

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New 2-(N-Substituted Carboxamidomethyl Thio)- Naphth[1,2-d]Oxazoles—Part V

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Several 2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth [1,2-d]oxazoles (II and III) and 2-(N-p-aryl sulphonanilido carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (IV and V) have been prepared via the interaction of naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiols with different N-aryl chloroacetamides and/or N-(p-aryl sulphonanilido)chloroacetamides respectively. Moreover, oxidation of some 2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (IIa, d, e, i and o) to the corresponding sulphones (Va-Ve) were undertaken. The biological activities of the compounds (IIa-III and IIIa-IIIi) were screened against some bacteria and fungi.

BASIC acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted with aromatic¹ or heterocyclic² moieties have been prepared in large numbers as potential local anaesthetics. Several basic N-(2-thienyl/furfuryl) acetamides have been patented as analgesic and antispasmodics³. Further, condensed oxazole derivatives possess valuable biological properties⁴⁻⁶. Recently, some biologically active naphthoxazole sulphonamides⁷, sulphonic esters⁸, thiosulphonic esters⁹, thiols⁹, alkylmercapto⁹, arylmercapto¹⁰ and acridinomercapto⁹ were synthesised in our laboratories.

The remarkable biological activities of these naphthoxazoles motivated us to synthesise some new N-substituted carboxamidomethyl thio naphth-[1,2-d]oxazoles (II-V) and to evaluate their antimicrobial activities.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. UV spectra in spec. pure ethanol were taken on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet spectrophotometer. NMR spectra in DMSO recorded on a Varian, 60 MHz NMR. The time allowed for the completion of the reaction, and the purity of the prepared compounds were controlled by tlc.

Reaction of naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiols⁹ (I) with N-aryl-2-chloroacetamides: Formation of 2-(N-substituted carboxamidomethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (II-V). Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol⁹ (0.001 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of an equivalent amount of KOH and the appropriate N-aryl chloroacetamide (0.001 mole) or N-(p-aryl sulphonanilido)chloroacetamide was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 30 min, concentrated and cooled, when a

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS II, III AND V

Compound*	m.p. °C
IIa	144-45
IIb	155-56
IIc	210-11
IId	176-77
IIe	145-46
IIf	183-84
IIg	160-61
IIh	140-41
IIi	234-35
IIk	174-75
III	139-40
III _m	124-25
III _n	179-80
III _o	158-59
III _a	> 360
III _b	250-51
III _c	312-13
III _d	266-67
III _e	309-10
III _f	> 360
III _g	327-28
III _h	> 360
III _i	> 360
III _j	> 360
III _k	356-57
III _l	> 360
III _n	> 360
III _o	323-24
IV _a	182-83
IV _b	> 360
V _a	198-99
V _b	244-45
VII _a	245-47d
VII _b	145-47
VII _c	185-88d
VII _d	205-10d
VII _e	160-61

* Compounds IIa-o, IIIa-o, IVa-b, Va-b and Va-e were obtained in 70-80, 73-90, 75, 60 and 50-65% yields, respectively. All the compounds gave consistent C, H, N and S analysis.

mixture of the crude compounds II, III or/and IV, V and potassium chloride was precipitated.

Acidification with acetic acid, filtration, removal of potassium chloride by water washing and recrystallization from ethanol gave II or/and III (Table 1).

2-Naphth[1, 2-d]oxazole thioacetic acid (VI) was prepared by the above method, through the interaction of naphth[1, 2-d]oxazole thiol (Ia) and monochloroacetic acid in ethanol and KOH. The compound (VI) was recrystallized from ethanol in about 70% yield, m.p. 205°, R_f 0.82 (benzene and ethylacetate mixture 9 : 1) (Found : C, 60.06 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 5.34 ; S, 12.48. Calcd. for C₁₈H₉NO₂S ; C, 60.23 ; H, 3.47 ; N, 5.40 ; S, 12.35%).

Reaction of 2-naphth[1, 2-d]oxazole thioacetic acid (VI) with aromatic amines : A mixture of compound VI (0.001 mole), aromatic amine (0.001 mole) and N-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1, 2-dihydroquinoline¹¹ (EEDQ) (0.001 mole) was dissolved in DMF (4 ml). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr, then seeded. The product was recrystallized from ethanol into compounds (IIa-h).

(II ; X=H)
(III ; X=SO₂H)

Ar	Ar
a ; C ₆ H ₅	i ; C ₆ H ₄ -COOH- <i>p</i>
b ; C ₆ H ₄ -Cl- <i>p</i>	j ; C ₆ H ₄ -OH- <i>p</i>
c ; C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	k ; C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ - <i>o</i>
d ; C ₆ H ₄ -Br- <i>p</i>	l ; C ₆ H ₄ -Cl- <i>o</i>
e ; C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	m ; C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>o</i>
f ; C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i>	n ; C ₁₀ H ₇ - α
g ; CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	o ; C ₁₀ H ₇ - β

Oxidation of 2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (IIa, IIc, IIe, IIi and IIo) with hydrogen peroxide^{10,14} : Formation of sulphones (Va-d) : To a solution of thioether (IIa, IIc, IIe, IIi or IIo) (0.005 mole) in acetic acid (5 ml) was added hydrogen peroxide [5 ml, 30% (w/v)], the reaction mixture warmed on a water-bath for 1 hr, cooled and diluted with water. The separated sulphone (Va, Vb, Vc, Vd or Ve) was recrystallized from ethanol, yield (50-65%) (Table 1).

(IV ; X=H)
(V ; X=SO₂H)

R
a ; H
b ; OH ₂

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation, a series of new substituted carboxamido methyl thio-naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (II-V) has been prepared (c.f. Table 1). These compounds are stable as indicated from their resistance to boiling water, hot 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH solution and can be recrystallized from organic solvents. Naphthoxazole sulphonic acid derivatives, III and V, show an outstanding violet fluorescence in organic solvents (methanol, ethanol, butanol and ethylene glycol).

Compounds II-V have been identified by a combination of their elemental analysis and spectral data. The ir spectra showing absorption bands at 3430-3350 cm⁻¹ (NH amide)¹², 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide)¹², 1630-1610 cm⁻¹, 1610-1580 and 1570-1540 cm⁻¹. The last three bands were assigned to the vibrations arising from the heterocyclic oxazole system^{8,9,12}. Substituted 2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (IIb-IIm and IIIa-IIIo) showed, in addition, the bands characteristic of the substituent groups, e.g. at 1350 cm⁻¹ for the NO₂ group, at 3535 cm⁻¹ for the OH group and two vibration bands at 1060 cm⁻¹ and 650 cm⁻¹ for the sulphonic group¹².

The uv spectra of naphthoxazole compounds (IIa-IIg) showed three λ_{max} at 280-290, 310-315 and 330-340 nm similar to substituted naphthoxazoles⁸.

The nmr spectrum of compound (IIa) showed the following signals at δ =3.24 (s, 2H, CH₂) ; δ =4.4 (s, 1H, NH) and δ =7.9-7.2 (m, 11H, aromatic), which are in accordance with its structure.

2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethylthio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (IIa-IIh) could also be obtained through an alternative route by condensation of 2-naphth[1, 2-d]oxazole thioacetic acid (VI) with different aromatic amines in the presence of N-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1, 2-dihydroquinoline (EEDQ)¹¹ as condensing agent and DMF as a solvent.

2-(N-aryl carboxamidomethyl thio)naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles compounds IIa, IIc, IIe, IIi and IIo were converted by hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid^{10,14} to the corresponding sulphones (VIIa-VIIe). Elemental as well as spectroscopic analysis of sulphones (VIIa-VIIe) are in accordance with the suggested structures. The ir spectra show an absorption band at about 1340-1320 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the sulphone group^{10,12}.

VII

Ar	Ar
a ; C ₆ H ₅	c ; C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>
b ; C ₆ H ₄ -Br- <i>p</i>	d ; C ₆ H ₄ -COOH- <i>p</i>
	e ; C ₁₀ H ₇ - β

Antimicrobial activities: The antimicrobial activities of the compounds of the types IIa-III, IIIa-IIIi, IVa and Va were tested *in vitro* against bacteria¹⁵, including gram-positive and gram-negative, such as *Staphylococcus albus* and *Bacillus megatherium* and against fungi¹⁶, such as *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium notatum*. The results indicated that most of the compounds (II and III) showed feeble (25%) to moderate (75%) inhibition at a concentration of 20 mg/l.

The compounds more active against *S. albus* are IIa, IIc, IIIa, IIIe and Va, against *B. megatherium* are IIa, IIb, IIIb, IIIe and IIIi, against *A. flavus* are IIc, III and IIIi and against *P. notatum* are IIc, III, IIIa, IIIb, IIIe, IIIi and Va.

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